

Semantic Transformation of French Phraseological Units

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Published online: 22 November 2021	The actualization of phraseological units, mainly the creation of humor or humor in a particular text, is based on a general stylistic need. This type of actualization is distinguished by the fact that the compound is understood simultaneously, in the same text in the sense of a phrase and in the sense of a free compound. There are two ways to understand and use a compound in a person's speech. The main condition for two different understandings is the situational context, extra-linguistic factors. The media is rich in such contextual contexts.
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INTRODUCTION

In linguistics there is a generally accepted view for each event, which indirectly determines the presence of a positive or negative component of the assessment within the phraseological units. Linguistic and non-linguistic factors are important in interpreting events in different situations within a society.

The connotative side of phraseological units includes some peculiar images, as well as emotional, expressive, evaluative and stylistic coloring. It is in the French phraseological units that the most stable part of the phraseological units can be said to be figurative [Cherdantseva, 1982, p. 145]. We know that the semantic meanings of phraseological units are connected with conceptual categories of the real world, such as processes, actions, events. In the semantic structure of such phraseological units, the definite article prevails over the denotative. The connotative side of their meaning is usually an evaluative, expressive, and emotional component.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

It is impossible to imagine the study of phrases without an in-depth study of the composition of phraseological units. It is well known that the essence of the formation of phraseological units can be understood only by studying the structure and basic semantic properties of lexemes, referring to the variable combinations of most phraseological units consisting of word components. When studying the phraseology of the French language, it is important to identify the national-cultural peculiarities and the words they are involved in the process of phrase formation.

In linguistics, a number of studies have been conducted in the field of structural, lexical, semantic and lexico-semantic transformation of phraseological units, their longitudinal and occasional applications. In world linguistics, it is recognized that all elements of language can be transformed. As a result of the transformation of language elements, lexicalization, grammaticalization, phraseological phenomena occur. In particular, the phenomenon of grammarization occurs on the basis of the transformation of lexical meaning into grammatical meaning, and the phenomenon of lexicalization occurs on the basis of the transformation of the meaning of the compound into the meaning of the word. The various structural and semantic changes of phraseological units, the constant combination of words to become a phraseological unit must have a figurative meaning, a figurative meaning. The meanings of phraseological units are based on semantic transformations and are the main feature that distinguishes them from other linguistic units. Based on the use of language units in a non-specific function and meaning, the transformation results in a free connection or a phraseological meaning that does not arise from the correct meaning of the sentence. For example: *avoir plusieurs casquettes-exercer plusieurs rôles, fonctions, dans différentes activités* (Perform multiple roles, functions in different activities), *avoir plusieurs cordes à son arc-Avoir différents compétences, plusieurs moyens d'arriver à un but* (having multiple tools to achieve a goal) on the basis of lexemes is also perceived as a free compound that can be interpreted as: *J'ai la chance d'avoir plusieurs casquettes et de pouvoir prendre celle que vous voulez me voir porter* (I am lucky to have a few hats and get what you want me to wear.). In this sentence, the words “avoir-to

have”, “*casquettes*-headgear (hat)”, “*plusieurs* -several” from the mutually compatible spiritual and syntactic combination of “*avoir plusieurs casquettes* -several heads to have clothes”.

At the same time, based on the semantic transformation of the free link, the term refers to a hat (policeman, baseball player, etc.) that belongs to a typical form of the profession that is not specific to the word-components in its composition. and the image of the free connection “*avoir plusieurs casquettes*” is expressed in the phraseological sense formed: *Il avait plusieurs casquettes: homme d'église, politique, écrivain et humoriste* (He had several professions: priest, politician, writer, and entertainer).

Faire le pont (to rest), *chercher une aiguille dans une boîte de foin*, (to look for a needle in a haystack), *passer du coq à l'âne* (to talk from a garden to a mountain), *couper les cheveux en quatre* (problem in phraseological units such as confuse), their phraseological meaning is based on the semantic transformation of the free connection. The differential criterion that distinguishes phraseological units from free connections is semantic transformation and imagery. G.G. Sokolova states that the formation of phraseological units is a phenomenon of transposition [2]. The coherence and ability of words in phraseological units to ensure their structural, lexical, and semantic transformation. This necessitates a methodological and semantic-pragmatic study of phraseological units. One of the means of formation of phraseological units is the semantic transformation of compounds. Therefore, phraseological units in language are considered as a semantic phenomenon.

As a whole, a phrase can move from one concept to another, and the meaning of a free connection can be transformed into a phraseological unit. Thus, depending on the meaning of the words in the phraseological unit, they can be called interpretable and unexplained units. They are transformed into certain semantic, lexical, lexical-semantic, and semantic-syntactic.

Phraseological units such as *Après la pluie, le beau temps* -the moon is fifteen dark, fifteen light (literally: the air is clear after the rain), *Jouer avec le feu* -to play with fire, *Se croiser les bras*-doing nothing are interpreted on the basis of the specific meanings of the lexemes they contain, and they are also understood in the form of free connections.

Chercher une aiguille dans une boîte de foin, the phraseological unit (looking for a needle in a haystack) is used as a free link, and the syntactic and syntactic combination of the words in it conveys the specific meanings of the words in the sentence.

In “*On a requis la liste de tous les appels entrants sur les déplacements de Laura, Mais ça va revenir à chercher une aiguille dans une boîte de foin* - we asked for a list of all incoming calls from Laura's travels, but it's like looking for a needle in a haystack”, the transformation of the meaning of the free conjunction forms its meaning, which is peculiar to the phraseological unit (impossible to do).

At the same time, on the basis of the semantic transformation of the free connection, the meaning of “impossible work” is formed, which is not specific to the word-components. In the free connection and the phraseological unit formed on this basis, figurativeness is the logical basis and shows the connection between them. Phraseological meaning emerges from the semantic transformation of a free connection such as *Après la pluie, le beau temps, jouer avec le feu, se croiser les bras*.

However, compounds such as *avoir des oreilles d'âne, quand les poules auront des dents*, are not based on free connections, they are not perceived as free connections, in human activity, “having a donkey's ear”, “(when) chicken teeth (when there is)”. In this case, the use of a phrase in a non-specific way, based on semantic transformation, forms the meaning of the phraseological unit. That is, links that are not interpreted on the basis of lexeme-specific meanings, that do not take into account lexeme-specific lexical meanings *avoir un chat dans la gorge*(avoir de la difficulté à faire sortir les sons de sa gorge), *donner sa langue au chat*(laisser tomber), *à cœur ouvert* (franchement, avec sincérité) *avoir des yeux de lynx* (avoir une vue perçante.), *avoir du sang bleu*(être d'origine noble), *du matin au soir et du soir au matin*(sans interruption, sans arrêt) will be.

The meanings of such phraseological units are contradictory to the meanings of the lexemes, and the meanings of the phraseological units are not interpreted on the basis of the meanings of the lexemes in these connections, the meanings of the phraseological units are formed by semantic transformation. The factor that connects them with free connections is semantic transformation and imagery, more precisely, the main criterion that distinguishes phraseological units from free connections.

In phraseological units, this or that action, the reflection of the event, the image must be embodied. Phraseologization is not only a linguistic phenomenon, but also a product of the development of the human mind, a linguo-philosophical phenomenon.

In French, as in any other language, a complex linguistic unit is formed on the basis of the semantic-syntactic transformation of phraseological units. *Aller de bouche en bouche, passer de bouche en bouche, se transmettre de bouche en bouche*, variant phraseological units or contradictory *Garder bouche cousue* (ne rien dire, garder silence, garder le secret) based on changes in certain components of the phraseological unit new phraseological units are formed and used in speech. In this sense, the linguo-cognitive, semantic-pragmatic study of phraseological units determines the speech potential of the compound. New structural phraseological units are formed as a result of the addition and subtraction of components in the structure of a phraseological unit for the purpose of strengthening its meaning, increasing its emotional expressiveness.

Alternative phraseological units such as *Chercher une aiguille dans une boîte de foin, chercher une aiguille*

dans un tas de paille (se dit de quelque chose qui est difficile à trouver) are being transformed. The transformation of phraseological units is characterized by the existence of a formal connection between the free connection and the phraseological unit, the fact that the free connection and the phraseological units belong to the same functional group, the semantic relationship between the free connection and the phraseological units.

Phraseological units are semantically transformed relative to free connections; most phraseological units are based on free connections and are phraseologized on the basis of semantic transformation.

Phraseological units such as *Aller droit au cœur (toucher, émouvoir)*, *lever le coude (prendre un verre d'alcool, boire de l'alcool)*, *Être armé jusqu'aux dents (être bien préparé)*, *avoir perdu la main (avoir perdu l'habitude)*, *Dresser l'oreille (porter attention)* (porter attention) are not based on free association. These phraseological units motivate on the basis of comparison of concrete objects, human-specific classification, abstraction, analysis, synthesis and other thinking operations, thinking of images of things-events. It is understood that phraseological units can be spontaneous in nature, based on the transfer or application of meaning.

Phraseological units are semantically transformed on the basis of linguistic factors such as linguistic and extralinguistic factors, naming, metaphor, metonymy, and synecdoche: Phraseological units such as *avoir un cœur en or, rouler sur l'or, l'or du soir, (Je ne regarderai ni l'or du soir qui tombe, Ni les voiles au loin descendant vers Harfleur, Et quand j'arriverai, je mettrai sur ta tombe Un bouquet de houx vert et de bruyère en fleur. Victor Hugo, Demain, dès l'aube..., 1856), boire une verre (c'est bien sûr le liquide contenu dans le verre que l'on boit, et pas le verre)* are spontaneous, and the association of similarities is a product of metaphor and metonymy. They are not used as free links. Based on the metaphor, there are bases of movement, such as the object of analogy, the image of analogy, the symbol of analogy, and the simile image of phraseological units is always present.

CONCLUSION

To conclude, the semantic relationship between the general phraseological unit and the newly formed phraseological units is preserved. In the process of semantic transformation, semantic transformation takes place; the meanings of phraseological units are actualized.

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